

VISCOELASTIC STRESS-STRAIN ANALYSIS DURING MOISTURE UPTAKE UNDER TENSILE CREEP

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SUMMARY

Viscoelastic analysis of stress-strain state is performed for model epoxy polymer during moisture uptake under tensile creep. Comparison with elastic case is given. The effect of stress level and ambient atmosphere relative humidity is given.

Keywords: viscoelasticity, moisture, sorption, swelling, stress, elasticity.

INTRODUCTION

Moisture effect on mechanical properties of rigid polymers like epoxies and composites is a relevant question during several decades. It is well known that moisture sorption process is relatively slow and hygroscopic equilibrium of those materials with wet environment could be achieved in several months and even years. Non equilibrium moisture distribution in cross section leads to swelling stresses in material during that period. This complex phenomenon could be accompanied by mechanical stress applied to the specimen (e.g. structures in civil construction during service in wet environment) and was investigated by several authors [1 - 3].

The objective of the research was to estimate stress-strain state of model polymer under tensile creep during moisture uptake performing viscoelastic analysis.

ANALYTICAL MODEL DESCRIPTION

The predictions for stress-strain state of a polymer plate under tensile creep during moisture can be obtained using the classical lamination theory approach. The plate is divided into plies. The constitutive models are defined at the ply level. The plane of a single isotropic viscoelastic ply is defined by the 1-2 coordinated system, where the 1 and 2 axes are general axis since the material has no preferred orientation. Consider a ply subjected to a plane stress state $\{\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \tau_{12}\}$ that may change with the time. The total strains induced within the ply are given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11}(t) \\ \varepsilon_{22}(t) \\ \gamma_{12}(t) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11}(t) & S_{12}(t) & 0 \\ S_{12}(t) & S_{22}(t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66}(t) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11}(t) \\ \sigma_{22}(t) \\ \tau_{12}(t) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Assuming that compliance terms $S_{11}(t)$, $S_{22}(t)$ and $S_{66}(t)$ are time-dependent, the Poisson coefficient, ν , is time independent and the material is linear viscoelastic and isotropic, the total ply strains induced by an arbitrary stress history are given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11}(t) \\ \varepsilon_{22}(t) \\ \gamma_{12}(t) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S & -\nu S & 0 \\ -\nu S & S & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2(1+\nu)S \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11}(t) \\ \sigma_{22}(t) \\ \tau_{12}(t) \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11}(t) \\ \varepsilon_{22}(t) \\ \gamma_{12}(t) \end{Bmatrix}_{\text{VE}} + w(t) \begin{Bmatrix} \beta \\ \beta \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11}(t) \\ \varepsilon_{22}(t) \\ \gamma_{12}(t) \end{Bmatrix}_{\text{VE}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \int_0^t \Delta S(\Psi - \Psi') \frac{d\sigma_{11}(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \\ \int_0^t \Delta S(\Psi - \Psi') \frac{d\sigma_{22}(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \\ 2(1+\nu) \int_0^t \Delta S(\Psi - \Psi') \frac{d\tau_{12}(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2a)$$

with the correspondent reduced times Ψ and Ψ' given by

$$\Psi = \int_0^t \frac{d\tau'}{a_w}, \quad \Psi' = \int_0^{\tau} \frac{d\tau'}{a_w}, \quad (2b)$$

where a_w is the horizontal moisture shift factor. The kernel $\Delta S(t)$ represents the time-dependent compliance and β is the hygroscopic expansion factor which depends on the moisture content $w(t)$ in percentage.

In order to eliminate the Volterra-type integrals, the transverse and shear compliance are expressed using Prony series, as Gramoll [4] and Czyz [5] have already discussed.

$$\Delta S(t) = \sum_{i=1}^M S_i (1 - e^{-\lambda_i t}) \quad (3)$$

where $S_i, \lambda_i, i=1..M$ are linear viscoelastic parameters. For example substituting (3) into (2), for the transverse strain, we obtain

$$\varepsilon_{22}(t) = S\sigma_{22}(t) + \sum_{i=1}^M \varepsilon_{i,22}(t) + \beta w(t) \quad (4)$$

where

$$\varepsilon_{i,22}(t) = S_{i,22} \int_0^t \left(1 - e^{-\lambda_i(\psi - \psi')}\right) \frac{d\sigma_{22}}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (5)$$

After some transformations, equation (5), gives the relation between the internal strain $\varepsilon_{i,22}(t_{j+1})$ and $\varepsilon_{i,22}(t_j)$. Let us assume a linear variation during $t_j \leq t \leq t_{j+1}$ for the stress, $\sigma_{22}(t)$, as

$$\frac{d\sigma_{22}}{dt} = \frac{\sigma_{22}(t_{j+1}) - \sigma_{22}(t_j)}{\Delta t} \quad (6)$$

Let also assume that the function $\hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma)$ is also approximated by a linear variation as

$$\frac{d\hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma)}{dt} = \frac{\hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma_{22}(t_{j+1})) - \hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma_{22}(t_j))}{\Delta t} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma) = S_i \sigma_{22} \quad (7a)$$

Substituting (6) into (5) we obtain

$$\varepsilon_{i,22}(t_j) = \hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma_{22}(t_j)) - e^{-\lambda_i \theta(t_j)} \int_0^{t_j} e^{-\lambda_i \theta(\tau)} \frac{d\hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (8)$$

where $\theta(t) = \int_0^t \frac{d\tau'}{a_w}$. In order to calculate $\varepsilon_{i,22}(t_{j+1})$ in terms of $\varepsilon_{i,22}(t_j)$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{i,22}(t_{j+1}) = & \hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma_{22}(t_{j+1})) - e^{-\lambda_i[\theta(t_{j+1}) - \theta(t_j)]} \left[\hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma_{22}(t_j)) - \varepsilon_{i,22}(t_j) \right] \\ & - \int_{t_j}^{t_{j+1}} e^{-\lambda_i[\theta(t_{j+1}) - \theta(\tau)]} \frac{d\hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma)}{d\tau} d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The integral of (9) can be solved as

$$\int_{t_j}^{t_{j+1}} e^{-\lambda_i[\theta(t_{j+1}) - \theta(\tau)]} \frac{d\hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma)}{d\tau} d\tau = \frac{\hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma_{22}(t_{j+1})) - \hat{g}_{i,22}(\sigma_{22}(t_j))}{\Delta t} \cdot \frac{a_w(t_{j+1})}{\lambda_i} \left(1 - e^{-\lambda_i \frac{\Delta t}{a_w(t_{j+1})}} \right) \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta t = t_{j+1} - t_j$ and the following approximation was used

$$-\lambda_i \left[\theta(t_{j+1}) - \theta(\tau) \right] = -\lambda_i \int_{\tau}^{t_{j+1}} \frac{d\tau'}{a_w} \cong \frac{\lambda_i}{a_w(t_{j+1})} (t_{j+1} - \tau) \quad (11)$$

Substituting (10) into (9) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{i,22}(t_{j+1}) = & e^{-\eta_i \Delta t} \cdot \varepsilon_{i,22}(t_j) + \left[1 - \frac{1}{\eta_i \Delta t} (1 - e^{-\eta_i \Delta t}) \right] \hat{g}_i(\sigma_{22}(t_{j+1})) \\ & + \left[\frac{1}{\eta_i \Delta t} (1 - e^{-\eta_i \Delta t}) - e^{-\eta_i \Delta t} \right] \hat{g}_i(\sigma_{22}(t_j)) \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where

$$\eta_i = \frac{\lambda_i}{a_w(t_{j+1})}. \quad (12a)$$

The total strain for each layer, given by Eq. (2), can then be written as

$$\{\varepsilon(t_{j+1})\} = [S_{elast}] \{\sigma(t_{j+1})\} + \{R(t_{j+1})\}, \quad (14)$$

where the $\{R(t_{j+1})\}$ vector contains the viscoelastic strains and the swelling strains due to moisture, as given by Eq. (2). Since the vector $\{R(t_{j+1})\}$ depends on the present stress state of the k ply, an iterative procedure for each time step must be used until the stress state converges.

Taking into account the in-plane loads acting on the plate, the equilibrium equations in global coordinates are

$$\int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \{\sigma\} dz = \{N\}. \quad (15)$$

where h represents the total plate thickness. If we assume a constant stress at each ply using Eqs. (14) and (15) we obtain a system of equations that allow determining the in-plane laminate strain $\{\varepsilon\}$ and the stress state in each i^{th} ply $\{\sigma\}_i$ as

$$\begin{cases} \{\varepsilon\} - [S_{elast}]_1 \{\sigma\}_1 = \{R\}_1 \\ \{\varepsilon\} - [S_{elast}]_2 \{\sigma\}_2 = \{R\}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \{\varepsilon\} - [S_{elast}]_p \{\sigma\}_p = \{R\}_p \\ \{\sigma\}_1 h_1 + \{\sigma\}_2 h_2 + \dots + \{\sigma\}_p h_p = \{N\} \end{cases}, \quad (16)$$

where h_i represents the thickness of the i^{th} ply and the subscripts indicate the ply number.

In order to avoid large systems of equations the ply stress state given by Eq. (14) can be used in Eq. (15) to obtain the following condensed system of equations as

$$\sum_{k=1}^P [S_{elast}]_k^{-1} h_k \{\varepsilon\} = \{N\} + \sum_{k=1}^P [S_{elast}]_k^{-1} \{R\}_k h_k, \quad (17)$$

where h_k represents the thickness of k ply and P the number of plies used in the approach.

CLASSICAL MOISTURE SORPTION MODEL WITH A CONSTANT DIFFUSIVITY

This model [6], assumes that moisture sorption occurs only by diffusion, and, according to the first Fick's law, the diffusate flow density \mathbf{j} is directly proportional to the gradient of its concentration c

$$\mathbf{j} = D\nabla c, \quad (18)$$

where D is the hygroscopic diffusivity describing the rate of moisture sorption, which is independent of moisture concentration. For a non-stationary state, with account of the mass conservation law, the second Fick's equation is valid. For the case of one-dimensional diffusion along the x axis, when the specimen thickness is smaller than its length and width, it has the form

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2}, \quad (19)$$

where c is the moisture concentration in the specimen at the instant of time t .

The solution to Eq. (19) for a plane-parallel plate of thickness h , with initial $c(0 < x < h, t = 0) = c_0$ and boundary $c(x=0, x=h, t > 0) = c_\infty$ conditions, is the series [6]

$$c(x, t) = c_\infty - 2 \frac{(c_\infty - c_0)}{\pi} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - (-1)^k)}{k} \sin\left(\frac{\pi k}{h} x\right) \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\pi k}{h}\right)^2 Dt\right). \quad (20)$$

Integrating Eq. (20) across the plate thickness, the moisture content in the specimen is obtained:

$$w(t) = w_\infty - 2 \frac{(w_\infty - w_0)}{\pi^2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - (-1)^k)^2}{k^2} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\pi k}{h}\right)^2 Dt\right), \quad (21)$$

where w_∞ is the equilibrium moisture content in the specimen.

The previous formulation permits us to solve the creep problem of a polymer plate during moisture uptake. The method described here, and resumed in the flowchart depicted in Fig. 1, was adapted from a FORTRAN computer program previously developed for orthotropic laminates [7].

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the hygro-viscoelastic stress-strain calculation scheme.

MATERIAL DESCRIPTION

Hygroscopic properties of a model epoxy resin EDT-10 (technical name) were obtained with data taken from [8], while mechanical properties of the material were taken from [9]. Moisture sorption by the material follows Fick's law in a wide range of atmosphere relative humidity up to $\varphi = 98\%$ with average value of hygroscopic diffusivity approximately $D = 1.900 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{h}$. Moisture sorption isotherm has a nonlinear

character and is was approximated by empirical polynomial function $w_{\infty}(\varphi) = 0.0004\varphi^2 + 0.0087\varphi$, were both w and φ are in %, with maximal moisture content of the resin little less than 5%.

Absorbed moisture causes essential changes in material mechanical properties and swelling. Experiment indicates that swelling strain is directly proportional to moisture content of the specimen and hygroscopic expansion factor is approximately $\beta = 0.2 \%^{-1}$ that roughly gives 1% strain for a specimen fully moistened in atmosphere with $\varphi = 98\%$. Elastic and shear moduli drop approximately 10% from their initial value 3.5 and 1.2 GPa (respectively) with moisture content changes from dry to 5% by weight $\frac{1}{S} = [3.500 + 0.0005067w(t) - 0.01594w^2(t)] \cdot 10^3$ (MPa), $\nu = 0.4400$.

Linear viscoelastic behaviour was described with exponential creep function according (3) which includes the moisture-time superposition principle (8) with parameters of relaxation spectrum given in Table.

i	λ_i (s ⁻¹)	S_i (MPa ⁻¹)
1	8.272E-05	2.89E-06
2	2.051E-07	5.23E-05
3	5.603E-09	1.83E-04
4	2.789E-10	5.03E-04
5	1.870E-10	1.53E-03

Horizontal moisture shift factor was determined from direct creep experiments and approximated by an expression $a_w = \exp[-2.0680w(t) + 0.1720w^2(t)]$. All the properties of the resin were obtained as functions of the moisture content $w(t)$ (%) under stationary conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Elastic and viscoelastic analysis was performed to estimate stress-strain state of model polymer under tensile creep for applied external stresses $\sigma_{11} = 0, 5, \text{ and } 10$ MPa during moisture uptake in atmosphere with $\varphi = 77$ and 98% for thin plate specimen with thickness of 0.2 cm. Moisture distribution and respectively stress distribution across the specimen becomes essentially nonuniform during moisture sorption process. Example of stress distributions are given in Fig. 2 for two different time moments and external stress $\sigma_{11} = 10$ MPa. It is seen from the figure that stress distribution for elastic and viscoelastic solutions essentially differs. Of course for both solutions stress distribution curves start and finish to uniform distribution of 10 MPa in a given example; these curves coincide and are omitted in the figure.

The most essential difference in stresses for elastic and viscoelastic solutions is revealed for outer ply with $x = 0.005$ cm and middle ply with $x = 0.095$ cm. Time dependencies of stresses in these plies are given in Fig. 3 and it is obvious that this difference changes with time. These time dependencies have extremums as for tension in the middle ply as for compression in the outer ply. The high of strain extremum and its time position depends on external stress and relative humidity of the atmosphere which governs

swelling process, but it is obvious that elastic solution gives overestimation of maximal inner swelling stresses up to one quarter.

Fig. 2. Stress σ_{11} distribution, elastic (dashed lines, white dots) and viscoelastic (solid lines, black dots) solutions; external stress 10 MPa, $\varphi = 98\%$ at times $t \approx 1.6 \cdot 10^6$ (diamonds) and $1 \cdot 10^7$ s (squares).

Swelling strains are moisture content driven parameters. These strains for a whole specimen growth from 0 to equilibrium values with growth of moisture content and are equal in both directions 1 and 2 in absence of external stresses.

Fig. 3. Axial stresses time dependencies for elastic (dashed lines, white dots) and viscoelastic approaches (solid lines, black dots) for outer ply $x = 0.005$ cm (diamonds) and middle ply $x = 0.095$ cm (squares); zero external stress.

The swelling strain values for elastic and viscoelastic solutions are the same at the beginning of moisture sorption process (zero) and at the end (e.g. approx. 1% in the considered case), but the value for elastic solution is approximately 1/5 higher than this one for viscoelastic in intermediate phase of moisture sorption process.

Total strain during creep in wet environment was calculated using (1). Creep strain at external stress $\sigma_{11} = 10$ MPa in atmosphere with relative humidity 98% for elastic and viscoelastic approaches in longitudinal direction 1 and transversal direction 2 are given in Fig. 4. Actually creep strain in both directions longitudinal 1 and transversal 2 is a superposition of viscoelastic and swelling components. In the loading direction 1 these components are both positive while in the transverse direction 2 these two strain components act in opposite directions and so the deformation has extreme character. The extremum of strain and its time position depends on external stress and relative humidity of the atmosphere which governs swelling process. This extreme behaviour for transversal strain is a principal feature of viscoelastic approach. Generally the model is linear viscoelastic hence strains are directly proportional to applied external stress so all results obtained for external stress 5 MPa are similar to the presented ones.

Fig. 4. Creep strain at external stress $\sigma_{11} = 10$ MPa in atmosphere with relative humidity 98%; elastic (dashed lines, white dots) and viscoelastic approaches (solid lines, black dots). Longitudinal strain in direction 1 (diamonds) and transversal in direction 2 (squares).

So taking into account of viscoelastic strain component allows obtaining of more precise description of material behaviour in hygrothermal conditions, improving damage risk estimation and reliability of deformability prediction in wet environment.

CONCLUSIONS

The results indicate that stress-strain behaviour of the material in elastic and viscoelastic case, both in free state and under external tension creep are similar in general, but differs in some important details. Internal swelling stresses calculated using viscoelastic

approach are lower than these in an elastic case. So viscoelastic approach gives more realistic stress distribution and less dangerous forecast if maximal stresses will be compared with material strength. In the tensile creep case the viscoelastic strain component must be taken into account during non-stationary conditions. The moisture activated swelling and the viscoelastic strain are described. For the transverse strain these two components act in opposite directions and so the deformation has extreme character. The extremum of strain and its time position depends on external stress and relative humidity of the atmosphere which governs swelling process.

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